

Subgigawatt Relativistic Resonant S-Band Backward Wave Oscillator

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The resonant relativistic backward wave oscillator (RBWO) was initially developed for efficient generation of high-power microwaves in the S-band (frequency of 3.6 GHz) while maintaining a relatively short structure length (about 2.5λ). The high-current electron beam with the energy of 0.7–1.5 MeV and the strong guiding magnetic field (2–3 T as a rule) were crucial parameters for such BWO. In the present paper, we propose a new layout of RBWO operating at moderately relativistic beam energy (450–550 keV) and at guiding magnetic field values starting from 1.3 T. Compared to the previously published RBWO design, the length of the periodic structure in the proposed configuration is increased by one period. To obtain high efficiency, the length of the insert between the cutoff neck and the periodic structure and the profiles of two terminal corrugations (defining reflections from the boundaries of the periodic structure) were optimized using particle-in-cell code XOOPIC. For the RBWO proposed, the numerical simulations show the average output power of 1 GW and 27–28% efficiency for the beam energies of 500–550 keV.

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1. Introduction

In the last decade, one may observe the increasing interest in the development of powerful multi-gigawatt sources of high-power microwaves based on the relativistic backward oscillator (BWO). Representative examples of such generators are BWOs with a maximum power of 4.3 GW in the X-band (9.4 GHz) [1] and more than 5 GW in the S-band (3.6 GHz) [2] and relativistic klystron-like BWOs with the output power of 6.5 GW in C-band (4.26 GHz) [3]. Such research is of considerable interest and has applications in various fields of science and technology, such as relativistic microwave electronics, high energy density physics, plasma and electron beam physics, communication and radar systems, etc.

The resonant relativistic backward wave

oscillator (RBWO), developed by a research team from the High Current Electronics Institute in Tomsk, Russia, in 2002 [2], is hitherto one of the most promising high-power microwave (HPM) radiation sources of gigawatt power level. Single-mode generation at the frequency of 3.6 GHz with a maximum pulse power of 5.3 GW was obtained in experiments [2, 4]. Based on the resonant oscillator layout, the possibility of generating high-power microwave pulses with an efficiency of 14% was demonstrated for the power supply system based on explosive magnetocumulative generators [5]. The stable repetition-rate mode of BWO generation with the output power of 1 GW at a microwave pulse duration of 100 ns and repetition rate of 10 Hz has been successfully implemented [6].

The characteristic feature of the resonant BWO is the interaction of the electron beam with both backward and forward waves of periodic slow-wave structure. It is implemented by optimizing reflections from the ends of

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the slow-wave structure and by improving the longitudinal distribution of the RF field of the fundamental harmonic of the forward wave and the (-1st) harmonic of the backward wave. This increases generation efficiency by up to 30% in the range of electron beam power from 5 to 20 GW.

The further development of high-power microwave sources in various frequency bands is accompanied by the increase in requirements for the parameters and quality of high-current electron beams [7, 8]. Of fundamental importance are the challenges of generating high-voltage “quasi-rectangular” power supply pulses with stable parameters; providing “flat top” pulses and fast rise time of the pulse in a few ns [9, 10]; repetitively pulsed HPM generation; optimizing the profile of the guiding magnetic field to obtain electron beams with the low component of transverse velocity of electrons β_{\perp} with respect to their longitudinal one (so that $\beta_{\perp}^2 \ll \frac{1}{\gamma^2}$) etc. There is also the challenge of developing high-efficiency generation in BWO at a level of 1 GW at moderate, practically convenient electron beam energy in the range of 450–600 keV and at electron beam power of less than 5 GW.

Based on the numerical simulations, we propose a new layout of resonant BWO that operates at lower beam energies (moderately relativistic 450–550 keV) than the published prototype of RBWO [2, 4] and generates high-power microwaves (~ 1 GW) at a beam power of less than 5 GW.

2. Resonant BWO model in XOOPIC

The configuration of the proposed RBWO is shown in Figure 1. As in the RBWO prototype, it has a cylindrical insert between the cutoff neck and the periodic slow-wave structure (SWS). By matching the length of this cylindrical insert, the phase shift between the fundamental harmonic of the forward wave and the (-1st) harmonics of the backward wave can be adjusted. In order to implement the optimal conditions for the

interaction of the electron beam with the (-1st) harmonic of the backward wave and the fundamental harmonic of the forward wave, the partial reflection of the operating TM₀₁ mode from the ends of the SWS can be used, so the amplitudes of the terminal corrugations were varied in the numerical simulations. To improve BWO performance at moderately relativistic beam energies, the number of corrugation periods was increased (up to five periods).

Simulations and optimization of the considered RBWO were carried out using 2.5D particle-in-cell code XOOPIC [11]. The electron beam with the chosen values of current, energy, and velocity spread was injected into the computational domain from the left side (before the cutoff neck, see Figure 1). The uniform magnetic field was set inside the RBWO structure; at the right-hand side of the SWS the field was decreased to ensure the beam dumping to the desired location next to the output horn.

FIG. 1. The geometry of the proposed resonant BWO in XOOPIC: 1 – cutoff neck, 2 – cylindrical insert, 3,5 – terminal corrugations, 4 – periodic SWS, 6 – output horn, 7 – electron beam.

On the right edge of the computational domain, boundary conditions of the impedance type (PML – perfectly matched layer) were set, corresponding to the propagation of the wave into free space. The microwave power was determined

FIG. 2. Dispersion curve of the slow-wave structure of proposed RBWO.

FIG. 3. The S-parameters (transmission and reflection) of the electrodynamic structure of RBWO and the radiation spectrum for a beam energy of 550 keV.

by integrating the flow of the Poynting vector over the cross-section of the output horn. The calculated Fourier transforms of the r - and z -components of the electric field at several points near the right boundary were used to calculate the radiation spectrum.

The length of the cylindrical waveguide insert, the period and amplitude of the SWS corrugations, and the inner radius of the terminal corrugations were the main parameters analyzed in the numerical simulations.

The simulations were carried out for various beam energy and current values (beam energy

range from 400 up to 700 keV, electron beam impedance from 60Ω to 150Ω). The dependence of the HPM pulse power on the amplitude of the guiding magnetic field was also investigated.

3. Results of numerical studies of RBWO

As a result of the research, the optimal parameters for the configuration of the electrodynamic structure of the RBWO are found with :

- trapezoidal corrugation profile,
- structure period $D \approx 0.37\lambda_g$,
- average SWS radius $r \approx 0.29\lambda_g$,
- corrugation depth $h \approx \lambda_g/12$

where λ_g is the wavelength of the TM_{01} radiation mode of the circular waveguide containing the RBWO structure.

The graphs in Figures 2–3 show the so-called “cold” (i.e., in the absence of an electron beam) characteristics of the slow-wave structure of developed RBWO. The SWS dispersion curve at the TM_{01} mode is shown in Figure 2. The interception points of this curve with the straight lines shown on the graph correspond to the Cherenkov synchronism between electrons with energies of 400–700 keV and (-1st) spatial harmonic of the backward wave. The operation point of RBWO is far from the so-called π -point of the curve ($k_z D \sim \pi$). Figure 3 shows the calculated transmission and reflection for the used electrodynamic structure in the generation frequency band and confirms the high reflection of the operating mode TM_{01} from the terminal corrugations of the SWS.

Two RBWO configurations are developed, optimized for the beam energies of 400–500 keV and 500–700 keV, realizing in the numerical experiment generation efficiency level of 28%, similar to the prototype of RBWO [2, 4]. The only differences between these configurations are the

FIG. 4: Microwave power: instantaneous and averaged radiation power of RBWO for beam energy of 550 keV.

FIG. 5: Spectrum of the RBWO with a beam energy of 550 keV.

shapes of the two terminal SWS corrugations and the length of the cylindrical waveguide insert. The optimal electron beam impedance is 80Ω for both configurations. The rise time of microwave pulses is 22–23 ns. The generation of radiation power about 1 GW is obtained at the beam energy of 550 keV (see Figures 4-5).

Typical dependencies of the average power and frequency of RBWO radiation on the impedance of the electron beam and on the magnitude of the guiding magnetic field are shown in Figures 6-7. It can be concluded that, in the case of stable single-mode operation, the generation frequency depends on these parameters weakly. The dependence of the radiation power on the guiding magnetic field has a downturn at the field values below 0.5 T; the stable single-frequency generation appears only when the magnetic field is 1.1–1.3 T and above.

The calculated dependence of the average radiation power on the length of the cylindrical waveguide insert (L_{ins}) for the 450 keV RBWO configuration at a guiding magnetic field of 2.5 T is shown in Figure 8. Analysis of the presented dependence allows us to conclude that the optimization of the insert length, with all other parameters fixed, makes it possible to double the output radiation power.

FIG. 6. Average microwave power and radiation frequency as a function of the impedance of the electron beam (beam energy 450 keV).

FIG. 7. Microwave radiation power and frequency as functions of the magnitude of guiding magnetic field (beam energy 450 keV, beam current 5.6 kA).

4. Optimization of RBWO generation efficiency for various beam energies

Two RBWO configurations have been developed, the first one optimized for beam energies of 400–500 keV and the second one for energies of 500–700 keV (indicated below in Figures 9-10 as No. 1 and No. 2, respectively).

The main differences between these

FIG. 8. The RBWO radiation power as a function of the length of the insert L_{ins} between the cutoff neck and the periodic SWS.

configurations are the profiles of the two terminal SWS corrugations, which determine the level of partial wave reflection from the edges of the structure, as well as the length of the cylindrical insert. For example, in accordance with the graph of Figure 8, the optimal value of L_{ins} for RBWO of configuration No. 1 is 95 mm; for RBWO of configuration No. 2, it is about 70 mm.

FIG. 9. The averaged radiation power as a function of the beam energy for two configurations of the RBWO. The curve of the total beam power is also shown.

The results of optimizations of RBWO for different beam energies are shown in the graphs

FIG. 10. Generation efficiency as a function of the beam energy for two RBWO configurations.

of Figures 9-10, which present the achieved levels of radiation power and the efficiencies of RBWO generation. High generation efficiency is achieved with magnetic field of 2.5 T. The results of optimizations of RBWO for different beam energies are shown in Figures 9-10, which present the levels of radiation power achieved and the efficiencies of RBWO generation. High generation efficiency is achieved with the magnetic field of 2.5 T.

5. Conclusion

The results of the optimization of RBWO geometry for the 400–700 keV beam energies and for the guiding magnetic field starting from 1.3 T are presented. Based on numerical simulations, we propose a new layout of RBWO that operates with moderately relativistic beam energies (450–550 keV) in comparison with the known RBWO (with operating parameters 1.2–1.5 MeV and 2.5 T) [2, 4]. It can generate high-power microwaves of 1 GW level at the total beam power of less than 5 GW. Compared to the known RBWO structure [2, 4], the periodic structure of the proposed one contains one extra period (five periods in total), while the overall SWS length remains relatively short ($\sim 3\lambda$). The length of the insert between the cutoff neck and the periodic structure, as well as the profiles of two terminal corrugations that affect reflections from the boundaries of the periodic structure, have been also optimized. Summarizing, we have demonstrated an efficient approach to the design of the resonant BWO, providing powerful S-band generation at moderate values of the beam energy and guiding magnetic field.

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